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EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION IN MANAGEMENT DECISION MAKING IN NTC UNITS, WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE TEXTILE MILLS IN COIMBATORE

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Abstract

As there is more number of private textile units in Coimbatore which are going in good success, this paper is concerned with a question to know how the public units are competing and how the employees are feeling good self in coming out of their opinion. A study has done to know the existing level of Worker Participation in Management Decision making within the NTC Production units. Interview schedule and in-depth interview were the main research techniques adopted for data collection while chi square and percentage used to analyze the data collected for the study.

Results show that employees in organizations demonstrate a high interest in participation in the decision making process within their respective work places. However, the actual level of involvement in management decision making demonstrated by the employees was found to be relatively low.

The study reveals a growing desire of non-management employees in the work environment to exercise greater involvement in the decision making process of the enterprise. Majority of the employees informed that decisions taken at the committee meetings are implemented, has the positive opinion about the councils working and performance, the organization has been considering the pre-requisites of successful workers participation and feels that shop council and plant council benefit the organization to great extent.

KEYWORDS: Employees, Involvement, Worker Participation, Decision making, Attitude.

Introduction to the study

Worker participation implies arrangements designed to involve workers in the decision making process. This allows for workers' involvement in the initiation, formulation and implementation of decisions within the organization. The concept can also be understood in terms of a new approach to industry and society in which people want to be interested with the taking of decisions which have direct bearing on them. It refers to any arrangement which is designed to involve low cadre employees (workers) in the important decision making within the workplace. This implies that rather than saddling only a group within the organization (for instance, management) with the responsibility of making decisions, all those who are to be affected by these decisions (including the workers) would be involved in its formulation and implementation.

Statement of the Problem

G. Murali Manohari/ Employee Participation in Management Decision Making in NTC Units, with special reference to the textile mills in Coimbatore

Employees are the assets of every organization and their easy going in their work leads good turnover. They only know their limits of difficulties in their daily work. As a management, while taking a productive decision they have to get some notions from the employees. The denial of employees' active involvement in decision making is held to be one of the major causes of the problems which are manifested daily in the work lives of the modern employees.

The implication of these gives increasing exposure to a monetized society, rising education and wider contact among people resulting from the break-up of artificial barriers was to shift these aspirations to a more satisfying work experience, greater control over the organization of work, greater opportunity for personal development and wider scope in exercise of initiatives. Comparing to other private textile mills in Coimbatore the NTC units are going in very moderate and so about this study.

Objectives of the study

- To find the level of workers participation in Management decision making.
- To ascertain workers level of involvement in the decision making process of their work place.
- To find out the general attitude of workers towards worker participation in management decision making
- To determine factor which aid or hinder the observed level of participation
- To analyse the implication of workers participation to worker and their organization

About the Study Area

Coimbatore, the hub of textile spinning and weaving mills is known as Manchester of South India. The growing knitwear exports from nearby town Tiruppur and home textiles exports from Karur and handlooms from Erode has contributed to tremendous growth and demand for spinning and weaving mills in and around Coimbatore. Many textile mills has upgraded their textile machinery and increased the capacity to the growing needs of the textile market. With all this, the Coimbatore textile sector is expected to pass through a new phase, especially in technical textiles, eco-friendly textiles, green composites, etc.

The textile industry in south India has been established in different centres but a concentrated development has taken place only in Coimbatore area due to the availability of certain facilities like moderate climate, growing of cotton, availability of abundant labour, good transport facility, both the road and rail and availability of power from Pykara Hydel Station.

Coimbatore is one of the most industrialized cities in Tamil Nadu. Popularly known as “The Textile Capital of South India”, the city is situated on the banks of the Noyyal river. The second largest city in Tamil Nadu, it has a number of major textile factories, engineering firms, automobile parts manufacturers, healthcare facilities, educational institutions, etc. The city has also a number of small, medium and large textile mills.

Many textile mills have upgraded their textile machinery and increased the capacity to meet the growing needs of the textile market. Recently NTC modernized its mills namely, Murugan Mills, Cambodia Mills, Pankaja Mills and Sri Rangavilas Mills. It is also proposed to modernize Coimbatore Spinning and Weaving Mills and to set up a technical textile unit in Coimbatore to manufacture medical textiles.

About the Research Unit

The National Textile Corporation Limited (NTC) is a Central Public Sector Enterprise under the Ministry of Textile which was incorporated in April 1968 for managing the affairs of sick textile undertaking in the private sector, taken over by the government.

NTC – Southern Regional Office, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu take cares on Coimbatore Murgan Mills , Combodia Mills , Pankaja Mills , Sri Rangavilas Gng.Spg.&Wvg. Mil, Coimbatore Spg. & Wvg. Mills . As there are 5 textile units in Coimbatore for the production unit of NTC, These units alone are taken for the study

Reviews on Worker Participation Management

Chaudhari (1979) has emphasised the main aim of the scheme of the workers' participation in management. The article suggests that WPM is to help in increasing production and productivity and sharing the gains of productivity through more effective management and better industrial relations.” The attempts made in this regard by Government of India had been towards greater participation of workers in industrial management. However, all the endeavors by the government have failed in fulfilling the objectives for which they were attempted.

Gamji Parameshwara Rao (1977) gives an analytical framework at micro level for understanding the levels of workers participation in management.

Earnest Dale (1949) described four degrees of cooperation as (i) informational cooperation, (ii) advisory cooperation, (iii) constructive cooperation and (iv) joint determination.

V. G. Mhetras (1966) described five stages of participation; (i) informative participation, (ii) consultative participation, (iii) associative participation, (iv) administrative participation and (v) decisive participation.

Lucille Yarrington, Keith Townsend, Kerry Brown (2007) in their article have highlighted the changes to the industrial relations legislation, users in the possibilities in the context of changes and the way managers and union engage themselves. Many academics suggest the most recent changes to the Australian Work Choices legislation have provided an array of opportunities for business to alter their relations with unions and employees. However, there is a range of literature that suggests that many employers benefit from having unions; involved in their workplace. The article explores the factors that are present in 'good' union-management relations and analyses the way in which organizations might benefit from union involvement.

Methodology

A descriptive study was done with an objective to find out the Employee participation in the management. Through the distribution of questionnaire data were collected. Proportionate Stratified random technique was adopted to collect the data. The employees both contract and regular were taken as a common but their departments were taken as strata. 30 samples from each unit were collected and totally 150 samples were taken into the study. The NTC – Production units such as Coimbatore Murgan Mills , Combodia Mills , Pankaja Mills ,Sri Rangavilas Gng.Spg.&Wvg. Mill, Coimbatore Spg. & Wvg. Mills. As there are 5 textile units in Coimbatore for the production unit of NTC, These units alone are taken for the study

Hypotheses

The following testable hypotheses were formulated to guide the attainment of the objectives.

There is a relationship between employees' socio-economic status and the level of involvement in decision making such that:

1. An employee in higher job position tends to exercise more involvement in management decision making than another in lower job position.

G. Murali Manohari/ Employee Participation in Management Decision Making in NTC Units, with special reference to the textile mills in Coimbatore

2. An employee who possesses higher educational qualification would tend to show no influence in management decision making than other who possesses lower educational qualification.
3. A young employee would more likely demonstrate more involvement in management decision making than his older counterpart.

Analysis for hypothesis 1

An employee in higher job position tends to exercise more involvement in management decision making than another in lower job position.

Table 1: Relationship between Respondents Job Position and Involvement in Management Decision Making

Job Position	Involvement in Decision Making			
	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>Occasionally</i>	<i>Often</i>	<i>Total</i>
Low cadre	18 [38.3%]	20 [42.3%]	9 [19.2%]	47
Middle cadre	11 [20.0%]	23 [42.0%]	21 [38.2%]	55
High cadre	21 [43.8%]	13 [27.0%]	14 [29.3%]	48
Total				150
$\chi^2 = 7.5$; d.f. = 4; $P \leq 05$				

From the above table it is found that the job position of the employees could influence the decision making process. Based on the job position the employees take the opportunity themselves to involve in the decision making. There is a statistically significant relationship between respondents' job position and their involvement in management decision making. This finding demonstrates that the respondents' measures of involvement are related to their job position, while those who possess low cadre position exercise low measure of involvement, those with higher position.

Analysis for Hypothesis 2

An employee who possesses higher educational qualification would tend to show no influence in management decision making than other who possesses lower educational qualification.

Table 2: Relationship between Respondents Educational Level and Involvement in Management Decision Making

Job Position	Involvement in Decision Making			
	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>Occasionally</i>	<i>Often</i>	<i>Total</i>
Schooling	12 [26.1%]	12 [26.1%]	22 [47.8%]	46
Diploma	6 [26.1%]	9 [39.1%]	8 [34.8%]	23
UG	6 [17.5%]	14 [41.2%]	14 [41.2%]	34
PG	11 [23.4%]	21 [44.7%]	15 [31.9%]	47
Total				150
$\chi^2 = 3.74$; d.f. = 5; $P \geq 05$				

It is evidenced from these findings that an individual’s educational qualification could influence the level of involvement he could exercise. This finding is not surprising since those with higher educational qualification tend to have more knowledge about management decision making, and are also more likely to seize the opportunity to be involved in the affairs of their organizations.

There is no statistically significant relationship between respondents’ educational attainment and their involvement in management decision making. This finding demonstrates that the respondents’ measures of involvement are not related to their educational qualification.

Analysis for Hypothesis 3

A young employee would more likely demonstrate more involvement in management decision making than his older counterpart.

Table 3: Relationship between Respondents Age and Involvement in Management Decision Making

Age	Involvement in Decision Making			
	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>Occasionally</i>	<i>Often</i>	<i>Total</i>
Below 30	12 [18.5%]	21 [32.3%]	32 [49.2%]	65
31-40	16 [39%]	18 [43.9%]	7 [17.1%]	41
41 and above	13 [29.5%]	17 [38.6%]	14 [31.8%]	44
Total				150

$\chi^2 = 6.6$; d.f. = 4; $P \leq 05$

From the above table it is found that the Age of the employees could influence the decision making process. Based on the Age the employees take themselves the opportunity to involve in the decision making.

There is a statistically significant relationship between respondents’ Age and their involvement in management decision making. This finding demonstrates that the respondents’ measures of involvement are related to their Age. When they get more exposure and learning, the experience and the maturity they attain leads to good management decision making invariably of their age.

General Analysis and Findings

As evidenced the demographic composition reflects that 49.64% of the respondents are 31 – 40 years age, 44.87% of the respondents are UG educational, 44.87% of the respondents have 10 – 15 years of experience, 64.10% of the respondents are living in Urban Area and 57.44% of the respondents are in 20,001 – 30,000 of income.

64.1% of the respondents show willingness to accept chance, 66.41% of the respondents show willing to take new tasks, 72.56% of the respondents agreed to take initiative to help other employees, 68.97% of the respondents are agreed to identify future changes and 64.10% of the respondents agreed for always keep going when going gets tough.

60.85% of the respondents agreed for adapt to a difficult situation. 50.56% of the respondents agreed to focus completely on job duties.73.85% of the respondents agreed to give their best effort at work each day. 62.82% of the respondents agreed to invite the employees in their work. 66.67% of the respondents agreed to get excited about participating in management work, 68.85% of the respondents agreed to feel completely involved in management work. 72.56% of the respondents highly agreed to inspire to meet their goals at the work. 64.87% of the respondents strongly agreed regarding the readiness to contribute new ideas for growth of organization. 69.23% of the respondents agreed regarding the readiness to work overtime if required, 66.67% of the respondents agreed

G. Murali Manohari/ Employee Participation in Management Decision Making in NTC Units, with special reference to the textile mills in Coimbatore

regarding the willingness to shift to new line of work, 48.72% of the respondents are neutral for the satisfaction level towards current line of work, The majority (66.67%) of the employees under the study shows an average involvement level towards current line of work, 74.36% of the respondents agreed regarding the satisfaction towards their working culture.

Suggestions

The Workers Participation in Management is seems to be positive in the production units of National Textile Corporation Limited, Coimbatore. Management cooperation should be improved by free flow of communication and information with the workers. Management should develop a favorable attitude of workers towards the schemes of participative management. Effort should be made to stir up the workers at the enterprise level to understand the schemes. Management should take the proper steps to reduce the conflicts between the labor as well as top level.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study it could be concluded that workers in the study establishments are generally involved in the management decision making within their respective establishments. On the other hand, the workers generally demonstrated high interest in management decision making. The study confirmed that the workers demonstrated positive attitude towards involvement in decision making. However, it is found that workers in the Production unit of NTC demonstrated more involvement in management decision making more than their counterparts.

Workers who are subjects of this study generally demonstrated willingness to accept the responsibility of involvement in management decision making whenever such opportunity arises. This implies that while the workers are willing to accept the responsibility of greater involvement in management decision making they are not ready to challenge the management in this regard.

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